

RESEARCH PAPER

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Assessment of Phytoplankton Diversity and its Role in Biomonitoring Water Quality of Pitlakes in the Raniganj Coalfield, India

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Abstract

This work presents the detailed study of the composition and diversity of phytoplankton and its dynamics through different seasons in the pitlake ecosystem. Several pitlakes of Raniganj coalfield were selected for that purpose. A total of 66 species of phytoplankton belonging to 7 phyla and 10 classes of phytoplankton were recorded. Bacillariophyceae was the most prevalent class of phytoplankton, whereas Heterokontophyta was the most prevalent phylum. Several diversity indices such as Menhenik, Margalef, Dominance, Simpson, Shannon, Berger-Parker, Brillouin, and Pielou's Evenness index were calculated for each site and season. The highest diversity was recorded in the monsoon season, and the highest abundance was recorded in the post-monsoon season. Pitlakes showed a high level of phytoplankton diversity with very little dominance. Both the Shannon-Weiner diversity index and the Margalef index predicted the pitlakes to have a moderate level of pollution.

Keywords: Pitlake; Phytoplankton; Diversity index; Water quality

Introduction

Pitlake is an artificial water body created by opencast mining (Blanchette and Lund, 2016). Pitlakes possess unique deep and narrow structures, without a littoral zone and steep rock walls that enclose them, which makes them different from other natural water bodies (Kalin et al., 2001). As the pitlakes have been created by mining, the water quality is not of very good quality. This creates a harsh environment for life to sustain (Bernasconi et al., 2022). The water quality of pitlakes can be studied using indicator species. It will help to understand not only the pollution level but also the possibility of life in those pitlakes (Mondal et al., 2023). Biomonitoring is a method by which one uses biological indicators to understand the ecological health status. This technique is widely accepted as it helps to understand and categorize overall water quality. The result found from this method can further be integrated with other physicochemical parameters (Parmar et al., 2016). One such good bioindicator is phytoplankton (Chandel et al., 2024).

Phytoplankton are free-floating microorganisms capable of photosynthesis. They are the primary producers of any aquatic ecosystem and serve as the base of any aquatic food chain. As a result, overall aquatic food chain and aquatic health are dependent on phytoplankton making them a very important component (Dalu et al., 2022). The presence, absence and diversity of phytoplankton are affected by environmental change. Several studies have been conducted and confirmed the role of phytoplankton as indicator species. Phytoplankton abundance and diversity in an open lake is dependent on several abiotic factors like pH, nutrient availability, temperature, transparency and several biotic factors like predation and competition (Fekadu and Chanie, 2017). Phytoplankton also undergo seasonal fluctuations. They respond quickly to environmental change because of their

short life cycle. The diversity indices of phytoplankton are used to understand the status of water pollution and its impact on species dynamics (Fekadu and Chanie, 2017; Liu et al., 2022).

The study of phytoplankton in the pitlake ecosystem is scanty (Bernasconi et al., 2022). Raniganj Coal Field (RCF) is one very important coalfield and several pitlakes have been created and will be created in future (Palit et al., 2014). This water is used by local people for domestic purposes and fishing. Some studies showed that migratory birds also visit the pitlakes (Palit and Chaudhury, 2019; Palit et al., 2020). This makes pitlake an important water body whose ecological health must be monitored. There have been several works on pitlake ecosystem in RCF pitlakes (Palit et al., 2014, Palit and Chaudhury, 2019; Palit et al., 2020). Most of them focused on studying the physicochemical parameters and water quality. Only a few research works have been conducted on phytoplankton (an important water quality indicator and aquatic food chain regulator) in RCF pitlake (Saha et al., 2020, 2022). Those works were preliminary study with a little diversity analysis and limited to a very small number of pitlakes. So, a comprehensive work with detailed diversity analysis is needed to understand the status, diversity and seasonal variation of phytoplankton and its role in monitoring the water quality of pitlake ecosystem. Therefore, the primary objective was to understand the composition and diversity of phytoplankton of RCF pitlakes, to predict the seasonal variation of phytoplankton and to predict the pollution status of those pitlakes using diversity indices.

Material and Methodology

Study Site

The phytoplankton diversity of the Raniganj Coalfield area's pitlakes was thoroughly examined in this study. Seven pitlakes were selected in the Paschim Bardhaman district for that purpose (Fig. 1). RCF is West Bengal's biggest and most important coal mining area, significantly contributing to India's total coal output (Palit et al., 2017). Eastern Coalfield Limited is in charge of managing all of the chosen locations, which were created due to mining activities (Palit and Kar, 2019). This research location showed the presence of biological resources like macrophytes, crabs, snails, and fish, which are harvested by local inhabitants for consumption. The details of the study sites that were examined are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Study sites with detailed geographical information

S. No.	Name of the Pitlake	Short Name	Location	Block
1	Dalurbandh	DPP	23°42'46.0"N, 87°15'43.1"E	Pandabeswar
2	Belpahari	BPP	23°42'38.9"N, 87°14'25.2"E	Pandabeswar
3	Joyalbhanga-1	JBP1	23°41'40.5"N, 87°17'07.9"E	Pandabeswar
4	Joyalbhanga-2	JBP2	23°41'38.0"N, 87°17'13.8"E	Pandabeswar
5	Nagrakonda	NKP	23°40'58.4"N, 87°17'28.5"E	Pandabeswar
6	Kumardihi	KDP	23°40'06.1"N, 87°15'42.5"E	Pandabeswar
7	Gunjan Ecological Park	GEP	23°39'54.4"N, 87°01'48.1"E	Jamuria

Sampling and Analysis

Phytoplankton sampling

At each site, phytoplankton samples were collected using filtering methods with a plankton net with a mesh size of 25µm. The samples were moved to clean, acid-washed plastic tubes after filtering approximately 70 litres of water through the plankton net. The time frame for sampling was from 7 am to 10 am. After being appropriately marked, the algal samples tubes were taken to the lab for analysis. 4% formalin was used to preserve the samples that were obtained. In order to examine seasonal variation and determine the effects of mine contamination on phytoplankton, samplings were conducted during the study period, which was from 2021 to 2023, in three distinct seasons: pre-monsoon (March to May), monsoon (June to September), and post-monsoon (November to February).

Microscopic studies

Quantitative estimation was done for phytoplankton by Lackey's drop method modified by saxena (1987). The sample was mixed well and one drop (0.1 ml) was transferred on a slide with the help of a dropper. The sample was then carefully covered with a coverslip to avoid any air bubbles. The slide was then studied under a compound microscope at both lower magnification (10x) and higher magnification (40x). Rose Bengal stain was used for better observation. Phytoplankton counts were taken by moving the slide horizontally and vertically. A minimum of three replicates were taken, and the average count per mL was calculated. Phytoplankton count per litre was calculated using Lackey's Drop Method (Lackey, 1938), as mentioned in APHA (1985) and modified by Saxena (1987) (Saxena, 1987).

$$\text{Phytoplankton}/L = \frac{N \times C \times 10}{V}$$

N = number of phytoplankton counted in 0.1 ml.

C = total volume of concentrate in (ml).

V = total volume of water filtered through net in litre.

Fig. 1. Location map of our study area and their locations in India (top left), and in West Bengal (top right). The studied pitlakes are represented in deep blue circles with site code.

Identification of algal samples

The prepared algal materials were studied under high power Olympus trinocular microscope (Model No CH20i) in 10X to 40X magnification and photographs were taken. Identification was done with the help of monographs on Indian algae and other standard literature (Prescott, 1951; Philipose, 1982, 1984; Anand, 1998; Tiwari and Chauhan, 2008; Mahendra Perumal and Anand, 2009; Perumal et al., 2009).

Diversity index calculation

Diversity indices provide quantitative measures of species richness, evenness, and dominance, offering insights into the ecological stability and health of an ecosystem. Commonly used diversity indices include Menhienik index, Margalef index, Dominance index, Simpson index, Shannon index, Berger-Parker index (BP Index), Brillouin index, Pielou's evenness index (J).

Menhinick Index

$$\text{Menhinick Index} = \frac{S}{\sqrt{N}}$$

where S is the number of species and N is the total number of individuals.

Margalef Index

$$\text{Margalef Index} = \frac{S - 1}{\ln(N)}$$

where S is the number of species and N is the total number of individuals.

Shannon-Weiner Index

$$H' = - \sum_{i=1}^S (P_i \ln(P_i))$$

where P_i is the proportion of individuals of the i th species, given by:

Dominance Index (D)

$$\text{Dominance Index} = \frac{\sum n_i(n_i - 1)}{N(N - 1)}$$

where n_i is the number of individuals of the i th species and N is the total number of individuals.

Simpson's Index of Diversity (1 - D)

$$\text{Simpson's Index of Diversity} = 1 - \frac{\sum n_i(n_i - 1)}{N(N - 1)}$$

where n_i is the number of individuals of the i th species and N is the total number of individuals.

Berger-Parker Index (BP Index)

$$BP = \frac{N_{max}}{N}$$

where N_{max} is the number of individuals in the most abundant species and N is the total number of individuals.

Brillouin Index

$$H_B = \frac{\ln N! - \sum_{i=1}^s \ln n_i!}{N}$$

where n_i is the number of individuals of the i th species and N is the total number of individuals.

Pielou Evenness Index

$$\text{Pielou Evenness Index} = \frac{H'}{\ln(S)}$$

where H' is the Shannon-Weiner index, and S is the total number of species.

Result and Discussion**Taxonomic analysis of phytoplankton**

During our study, a total of 66 phytoplankton species belonging to 7 phyla and 10 classes of phytoplankton were identified. The top ten most abundant genus were *Navicula*, *Eunotia*, *Cocconeis*, *Amphora*, *Pinnularia*, *Cymbella*, *Synedra*, *Anabaena*, *Spirogyra*, *Oscillatoria*. Most abundant species include *Navicula sp.*, *Cocconeis sp.*, *Eunotia sp.*, *Eunotia pectinalis*, *Cymbella sp.*, *Synedra ulna*, *Anabaena sp.*, *Navicula gregaria*, *Oscillatoria sp.*, *Amphora sp.*

A detailed taxonomic study has been conducted to understand the contribution of different phyla and classes in our study sites. The most abundant phylum was Heterokontophyta, which represented around 40% of total species, followed by Charophyta and Chlorophyta, representing 29% and 11% of total species, respectively. Cyanobacteria phylum includes 10% of species (Fig. 2). Approximately 6% of species were not identified and put in the 'Unknown' group. The rest species belong to Ochrophyta, Miozoa and Euglenozoa. A similar trend can be seen in the contribution of phyla in the total number of individuals or abundance of phytoplankton. Phylum Heterokontophyta, Cyanobacteria and Charophyta were the three most dominant phyla, representing 74%, 14%, and 10%, respectively (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2. Phylum wise phytoplankton species distribution of all the study sites

When phytoplankton class-wise species representation was studied, it was found that Bacillariophyceae was the most dominant class, representing 39% of species. It was followed by Zygnematophyceae and Cyanophyceae, which represented 29% and 10%, respectively (Fig. 4). Chlorophyceae represented 9%. Class Bacillariophyceae also contributes to 73% of total

phytoplankton abundance, and Cyanophyceae represent 14%, and Zygnematoephyceae 10% of total abundance, making them the three most abundant classes (Fig. 5).

Fig. 3. Phylum wise phytoplankton abundance distribution and seasonal variation of all the study sites

Fig. 4. Class wise phytoplankton species distribution of all the study sites

Fig. 5. Class wise phytoplankton abundance distribution and seasonal variation of all the study sites

Diversity analysis of phytoplankton

Diversity indices were calculated for our seven sites. The average value of each index was calculated, taking the value of all three seasons. Maximum abundance was seen in the BPP site with a value of 3899 phytoplankton/litre, and minimum abundance was seen in JBP2 (2052 phytoplankton /litre). Richness was in the range of 29 to 49. The average value of the Menhinik index ranged from 0.63 to 0.89, of which the maximum value was found in GEP. GEP also showed the highest Margalef index of 5.04. The minimum Margalef index varied was 4.08 which was found in DPP. The dominance index value ranged from 0.06 to 0.09, which indicates that no particular species was very dominant. The Simpson index ranged from 0.91 to 0.94, and the Shannon-Weiner index varied from 2.89 to 3.13. Both the Simpson and Shannon indexes indicated a very high diversity in all seven sites. Berger-Parker index and Brillouin index were maximum in JBP1 and GEP, respectively. When Pielou's evenness index was calculated, the value ranged from 0.79 to 0.86, which shows a high level of evenness and lower dominance of a particular species. For each site, the season-wise change of different diversity index is shown in Fig. 6.

The average values of each index of all sites of each season were calculated to predict the seasonal change of phytoplankton diversity. The pre-monsoon season showed the highest evenness index.

The monsoon season showed the highest Mehinick index, Margalef index, richness, Simpson index, Shannon index, Brillouin index and lowest abundance, dominance and Berger-Parker index. Post-monsoon season showed the highest abundance, dominance index and lowest Simpson index, Shannon index, Brillouin index and evenness index.

Fig. 6. Seasonal variation of abundance, richness and different diversity indices, i.e. Menhenik index, Margalef index, Dominance index, Simpson index, Shannon index, Berger-Parker index (BP Index), Brillouin index, Pielou's evenness index (J), respectively of seven sites

Determination of pollution status using phytoplankton diversity

Several scientific studies have been conducted where the diversity index has been used to understand the pollution level of an aquatic ecosystem (Ghosh and Keshri, 2011; Ghosh et al., 2012; Al-Tae and Mahmoud, 2023). Two very important diversity indices that can predict pollution levels are the Shannon-Weiner index and the Margalef index.

Staub et al. in 1970 provided the relationship between the Shannon-Wiener Diversity Index and pollution status in water bodies (Table 2). If water bodies have a Shannon-Wiener diversity index between 3.0 and 4.5, they are slightly contaminated. Diversity index between 2.0 and 3.0 is considered as light pollution, between 1.0 and 2.0 as moderately polluted, and index between 0.0 and 1.0 is considered to be extremely polluted (Staub et al., 1970; Pore et al., 2020).

Table 2. Pollution status based on Shannon–Wiener Diversity Index (Staub et al., 1970)

Shannon–Wiener Diversity Index	Pollution Status
3.0 – 4.5	Slight Pollution
2.0 – 3.0	Light Pollution
1.0 – 2.0	Moderate Pollution
0.0 – 1.0	Heavy Pollution

Wihlm and Dorris, in 1968, classified pollution status into three levels. Shannon-Weiner diversity of less than 1 indicates heavy pollution and more than 3 indicates clean conditions. If the water body has a diversity between 1 to 3, it is considered moderately polluted (Table 3).

Margalef index is also used to predict the pollution status of water. Table 4 showed the relationship between the Margalef index and water pollution status (You et al., 2007). We have used two indices to predict the pollution status of our study sites in different seasons. Shannon index value ranged from 2.68 to 3.27. All the sites during pre-monsoon and post-monsoon seasons showed moderate

levels of pollution except for the GEP site. During monsoon season, all the sites showed clean water conditions except for JBP₁, which showed moderate water pollution. Overall, water quality indicates moderate pollution according to the Shannon-Weiner diversity index. Table 5 showed the value of the Shannon-Weiner index for each site in three different seasons and their pollution status.

Table 3. Pollution status based on Shannon–Wiener Diversity Index (Wihlm and Dorris, 1968)

Shannon–Wiener Diversity Index	Pollution Status
<1	Heavily Polluted
1–3	Moderately Polluted
>3	Clean Condition

Table 4. Water quality classification based on Margalef Index (D)

Margalef Index (D)	Water Quality Classification
0 – 1	More Serious Pollution
1 – 2	Serious Pollution
2 – 4	Moderate Pollution
4 – 6	Light Pollution
> 6	Clean Water

Table 5. Shannon-Weiner index and pollution status of study sites

Season	Site Code	Shannon Weiner Index	Pollution Status (Staub et al., 1970)	Pollution Status (Wihlm and Dorris, 1968)
Pre-monsoon	DPP	2.97	Light pollution	Moderately Polluted
Pre-monsoon	BPP	2.95	Light pollution	Moderately Polluted
Pre-monsoon	JBP ₁	2.88	Light pollution	Moderately Polluted
Pre-monsoon	JBP ₂	2.68	Light pollution	Moderately Polluted
Pre-monsoon	NKP	2.81	Light pollution	Moderately Polluted
Pre-monsoon	KDP	2.96	Light pollution	Moderately Polluted
Pre-monsoon	GEP	3.12	Slight pollution	Clean Condition
Monsoon	DPP	3.13	Slight pollution	Clean Condition
Monsoon	BPP	3.19	Slight pollution	Clean Condition
Monsoon	JBP ₁	2.97	Light pollution	Moderately Polluted
Monsoon	JBP ₂	3.08	Slight pollution	Clean Condition
Monsoon	NKP	3.27	Slight pollution	Clean Condition
Monsoon	KDP	3.15	Slight pollution	Clean Condition
Monsoon	GEP	3.23	Slight pollution	Clean Condition
Post-monsoon	DPP	2.97	Light pollution	Moderately Polluted
Post-monsoon	BPP	2.95	Light pollution	Moderately Polluted
Post-monsoon	JBP ₁	2.79	Light pollution	Moderately Polluted
Post-monsoon	JBP ₂	2.85	Light pollution	Moderately Polluted
Post-monsoon	NKP	2.85	Light pollution	Moderately Polluted
Post-monsoon	KDP	2.84	Light pollution	Moderately Polluted
Post-monsoon	GEP	3.06	Slight pollution	Clean Condition
Overall		2.98	Light pollution	Moderately Polluted

Table 6. Margalef index and pollution status of study sites

Season	Site Code	Margalef Index	Pollution Status (Jia et al., 2007)
Pre-monsoon	DPP	3.60	Moderate Pollution
Pre-monsoon	BPP	3.45	Moderate Pollution
Pre-monsoon	JBP ₁	4.40	Light Pollution
Pre-monsoon	JBP ₂	3.76	Moderate Pollution
Pre-monsoon	NKP	4.52	Light Pollution
Pre-monsoon	KDP	4.45	Light Pollution
Pre-monsoon	GEP	3.96	Moderate Pollution
Monsoon	DPP	4.58	Light Pollution
Monsoon	BPP	6.07	Clean Water
Monsoon	JBP ₁	5.83	Light Pollution
Monsoon	JBP ₂	5.43	Light Pollution
Monsoon	NKP	6.21	Clean Water
Monsoon	KDP	5.89	Light Pollution
Monsoon	GEP	6.49	Clean Water
Post-monsoon	DPP	4.05	Light Pollution
Post-monsoon	BPP	4.28	Light Pollution
Post-monsoon	JBP ₁	3.99	Moderate Pollution
Post-monsoon	JBP ₂	4.06	Light Pollution
Post-monsoon	NKP	3.86	Moderate Pollution
Post-monsoon	KDP	3.67	Moderate Pollution
Post-monsoon	GEP	4.65	Light Pollution
Overall		4.63	Light Pollution

The Margalef index also indicates different pollution levels. Margalef index value showed mostly the value of light to moderate pollution. Only GEP and BPP during monsoon showed clean water. Overall, the Margalef value was 4.63, which indicates light pollution. Table 6 showed the value of Margalef index for each site in three different season and their pollution status.

Conclusion

Our study has provided a detailed overview of phytoplankton composition, and its diversity and dynamics. Phytoplankton was found to be abundant in pitlakes, which indicates the sustaining aquatic food chain was present in pitlakes. During our study, a total of 66 phytoplankton species belonging to 7 phyla and 10 classes of phytoplankton were identified. The most abundant phylum of phytoplankton was Heterokontophyta, and the most abundant class was Bacillariophyceae. The harsh environment of pitlake and lack of nutrients could be the possible reason for that. The Phytoplankton community showed a prominent seasonal fluctuation. The abundance was minimal during monsoon season because of the dilution due to rainwater. The diversity indices value concluded that pitlakes have a high level of phytoplankton diversity with a very low amount of dominance. The diversity indices value also has seasonal fluctuation. The highest evenness index was observed prior to the monsoon season. The Mehinick, Margalef, Richness, Simpson, Shannon, and Brillouin indices were all highest during the monsoon season, while the abundance, dominance, and Berger-Parker indices were lowest. The dominance index and abundance were highest during the post-monsoon season, whereas the Simpson, Shannon, Brillouin, and evenness indices were lowest. The Shannon-Weiner and Margalef indices stated that pre-monsoon and post-monsoon water was moderately polluted in almost all the pitlakes and water was in a clean condition or in a very low pollution level during monsoon. Overall, the water quality of pitlakes was moderately polluted.

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NK and DP conceived the concept, wrote and approved the manuscript.

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Competing interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Ethics approval

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